

Pyrazolone Thiosemicarbazone Based Metal Complexes: Physico-Chemical Study, Synthesis and Biological Activity

Rashmi B. Patel¹, Dhanji P. Rajani², Smita D. Rajani², Hitesh D. Patel^{1*}

¹Department of Chemistry, School of Science, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-380009, Gujarat, India.

²Microcare Laboratory & TRC, Surat 395003, Gujarat, India

*Corresponding author: Hitesh D. Patel, Tel.:+91-079-26300969, E-mail: drhiteshpatel@gmail.com

Received: June 1, 2015, Accepted: July 9, 2015, Published: July 9, 2015.

ABSTRACT

In this article we have reported physico-chemical study of 2-((3-methyl -5- oxo -1- phenyl -4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methylene)hydrazinecarbothioamide with various metal ions such as Cu(II), Cr(II), Mn(II), Pd(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Pb(II) and Hg(II) by two methods spectrophotometry and conductometry. The study said that metal:ligand ratio is 1:1 and the further conformation is done by spectral analysis. We have also screened our compounds for antibacterial, antifungal and antimalarial activity.

Keywords: pyrazolone-thiosemicarbazone, metal complexes, physico-chemical study, antibacterial, antifungal, antimalarial activity.

INTRODUCTION

Pyrazolone and their derivatives are exhibiting exceptional biological and pharmacological properties [1, 2]. Recently, pyrazolone thiosemicarbazones and their metal complexes were synthesized for photochromic applications [3, 4] and other several of properties such as antitumor, antimicrobial, and antiviral activities [5, 6]. Literature review reveals that very little work, have been reported on biological studies, like DNA binding cleavage [7, 8], kinetic study (ligand - M-complexes) [9, 10], inhibition study [11].

As per literature we have found that two physico-chemical studies, UV-vis spectrophotometry and conductometry at 15°C, 25°C, 35°C and 45°C temperatures were not reported so we have carried out to find the metal:ligand ratio through the said techniques. Which are further confirmed by molar conductance vs. mole ratio, molar mole ratio techniques and Benesi-Hildebrand approach as well as spectral analysis comparison with complexes of the complex formation method. In the present study, we have also synthesized metal-ligand complexes of 2-((3-methyl -5- oxo -1- phenyl -4,5-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl) (phenyl) methylene) hydrazine carbothioamide with eight metal ions like Copper(II), Chromium(II), Manganese(II), Palladium(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), lead(II) and Mercuric(II) in methanol by solid complex formation method and characterized by IR, ¹H NMR, Mass Spectroscopy and TGA analysis.

Experimental

Materials and solutions

Analytical grade salts of metal ions, CuCl₂.6H₂O, CoCl₂.6H₂O, Pb(NO₃)₂.6H₂O, NiCl₂.6H₂O, PdCl₂.6H₂O, CrCl₂.6H₂O, MnCl₂.6H₂O, HgCl₂.6H₂O and HPLC gradient grade methanol were procured from Sigma Aldrich with purity of > 99 %. The conductivity of solvent was < 3.0 × 10⁻⁷ Scm⁻¹ at 25°C temperature. All reagents Ethyl acetoacetate, Phenyl hydrazine, Benzoyl chloride, Calcium hydroxide, 1, 4 Dioxane and Glacial acetic acid were purchased from finar chem. Ltd., Ahmadabad.

Instrumentation and conditions

The electronic absorption spectra were recorded in the region of 200–800 nm is using UV-visible spectrophotometer model JASCO V-530 with quartz cell of 1.0 cm path length. The spectra were recorded at a scan speed of 400 nm min⁻¹. The conductance measurement was carried out by using Metrohm 856 conductivity unit. The conductivity cell was calibrated with KCl solution in the appropriate concentration. A dip-type-cell having a cell constant of 0.98 cm⁻¹ was used. A thermostated water-bath was used to maintain a constant solution temperature at the desired significance having an accuracy of ± 0.5°C. Analytical balance, Sartorius GD503 (Bradford, MA, USA) having a readability of 0.0001 g was utilized for weighing of samples.

¹H-NMR spectra were measured in DMSO-d₆, using BRUKER, KP-B-01 NMR spectrometers and Thermal Analysis, at the National Facility for Drug Discovery Center, Rajkot. Infrared (IR) spectra were recorded on SHIMADZU with KBr pellets at Vaibhav analytical services Ahmadabad. Mass spectra were reported at Synzeal research laboratory, Gandhinager. Melting point was measured with a TECH XT-5 a melting point apparatus.

Synthesis of ligands

Synthesis of pyrazolone : Green, synthesis of 5-Methyl-2-phenyl-1, 2-dihydro pyrazol-3-one (PMP) was prepared by the standard method [12]. m.p. 126 - 128°C, yield= 82%. IR (KBr) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 3128, 1770, 1607, 1525, 1498, 976.

Synthesis of 4-Benzoyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one (PMBP): The PMBP was synthesized according to the modified method which was reported previously [13]. The preparation of PMBP from PMP (0.1 M) in 1,4-dioxane (5 mL) and Ca(OH)₂ (0.15 M) was added to this solution and then the Benzoyl chloride (0.1 M) was added drop wise, the reaction mixture was exposed to microwave irradiation (power input 360 W) for 15 min. Upon completion, the mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into cold HCl (50 mL 2M) with constant stirring. Reaction progress examined on the TLC plate in Ethyl

acetate: Hexane (3:2) as the mobile phase. m.p. = 90°C, yield = 95%, MS: m/z 279 $[M+1]^+$, molecular formula: $C_{17}H_{14}N_2O_2$, 1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ = 7.754-7.301(m, 10H), 2.505-2.234 (s, 3H), 3.173(s, 1H).

Synthesis of (Z)-2-((3-methyl -5- oxo -1- phenyl -4,5- dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl) (phenyl) methylene) hydrazinecarbothioamide:

Synthesis of PMBP-TSC was obtained by a mixture of the PMBP (5 mM) and thiosemicarbazide (5 mM) in ethanol (5 mL) and glacial acetic acid as a catalyst (1 mL)[14]. The reaction mixture was irradiated in microwave oven for the 6–8 min at 300 W power output. Reaction progress examined on the TLC plate in Ethyl acetate: Petroleum ether (2:4) as the mobile phase. m.p = 203°C, yield = 90%, MS = m/z 351.7 (M^+), molecular formula: $C_{18}H_{17}N_5OS$, 1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO): δ = 10.407 (s, 1H, -N(H)), δ = 9.37(s, 2H, -NH₂), 8.674-7.094(m, 10H, phenyl), δ = 3.168 (s, 1H, CH), δ = 2.51, 2.106 (s, 3H, CH₃).

Physico-chemical methods

Conductometric titration: In a typical experiment, a 50 mL of the metal salt (2.0×10^{-4} M) solution in methanol was placed in the titration cell. To maintain a constant temperature, it was joined to a thermostated circulator water bath and the conductance of the solution was measured. Then a known amount of ligand in methanol (0.5 mL, 2.0×10^{-3} M) was added in a stepwise manner using a calibrated microburette and the conductance of the solution was measured after string of each addition (1.0 min) and thermal equilibration. The experimental error in the temperature was minimized to $\pm 0.5^\circ C$. The similar process was followed at 15, 25, 35, and 45°C temperature, and the conductometric data were used for the calculation of the formation constant of the complexes in methanol at the preferred temperatures.

Spectrophotometric measurements: The stoichiometries of PMBP-TSC - M^{n+} complexes were determined by the molar ratio method [15] and Benesi-Hildebrand approach [16]. For mole ratio method, 0.2 mL (2.0×10^{-3} M) of the ligand solution in methanol was placed in the spectrophotometer unit and measured its absorbance. Then a series of fixed amounts of metal ions (2.0×10^{-4} M) was added in a stepwise by using 10 mL micropipette and after each addition of the solution the absorbance was measured at the respective wavelength maximum (λ_{max}). The metallic solution was added to the M: L was achieved at room temperature. For

spectrometric titration, the metal ion concentration were kept constant at 2.0×10^{-5} M and ligand was changed from 1.0×10^{-3} M and 1.0×10^{-2} M. The metal- ligand mole ratio ($C_M:C_L$) obtained in this case varied from 0.2 to 2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The conductometric study of PMBP-TSC with the metal salts of Cu^{+2} , Pd^{+2} , Co^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Mn^{+2} , Cr^{+2} , Pb^{+2} , Hg^{+2} ions. The molar conductance (Λ_m) of the solution was monitored as a role of mole ratio of $[L]/[M]$ in a pure methanol at different temperatures (15°C, 25°C, 35°C and 45°C) is shown in figure 1 (A-H). The plots (fig. 1) Show one evident graph; suggestive of that the probability stoichiometric ratio of complexes is M: L. In the all cases, the graphs of the corresponding Λ_m vs. $[PMBP-TSC]/[M^{n+}]$ plots change sharply at the point, where the ligand to cations mole ratio is one and its stable complex formation is 1:1. Such a conductance behavior is indicative of the formation of ML complexation. The 1:1 complexation of metal ion with ligand can be given by following equilibrium equation.

Where, L, M^{n+} , ML are ligand (PMBP-TSC), cation and complex respectively.

The complex formation constant of the complexes at each temperature was obtained from the deviation of molar conductance as a function of $[L]/[M]_t$ molar ratio plots using an origin computer program. The specifics of calculation of the complex formation constants K_f equation (4) of complexes by the conductometric method can be described as [17-20]. The values of the stability constant ($\log K_f$) complexation of metal ion and ligand are listed in Table 1.

$$k_f = \frac{[ML^{n+}]}{[M^{n+}][L]} = \frac{\Lambda_M - \Lambda_{obs}}{(\Lambda_{obs} - \Lambda_{ML})[L]} \quad (4)$$

Where, Λ_M = the molar conductance of the M^{n+} before adding of ligand, Λ_{obs} = the molar conductance of the solution for the period of titration. Λ_{ML} = the molar conductance of the complex, $[L]$ = the molar conductance of free ligand.

Synthesis of solid metal complexes

Figure-1: Molar conductance ($S\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$) vs. $[L]/[M^{2+}]$ graph for (A) Cu^{2+} , (B) Pd^{2+} , (C) Co^{2+} , (D) Ni^{2+} , (E) Mn^{2+} , (F) Cr^{2+} , (G) Pb^{2+} , (H) Hg^{2+} at (■) 15°C , (●) 25°C , (▲) 35°C , (▲) 45°C temperature in pure MeOH.

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters and formation of the stability constant ($\log K_f$) for metal–ligand complexes in methanol at different temperature

Cation	$\log K_f$				Thermodynamic parameters (25°C)		
	15°C Temp.	25°C Temp.	35°C Temp.	45°C Temp.	$-\Delta G^\circ_c$ (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔH°_c (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS°_c ($\text{J mol}^{-1}\text{ K}^{-1}$)
Cu^{2+}	2.412	2.440	2.479	2.499	6.920	2.313	30.98
Pd^{2+}	3.001	3.0732	3.111	3.145	8.816	5.948	49.54
Co^{2+}	2.497	2.563	2.647	2.707	7.354	5.452	42.97
Ni^{2+}	2.648	2.657	2.6611	2.664	7.622	0.743	28.07
Mn^{2+}	2.657	2.666	2.678	2.693	7.648	0.743	28.15
Cr^{2+}	2.705	2.723	2.730	2.735	7.812	1.487	31.20
Pb^{2+}	2.599	2.632	2.657	2.677	7.551	2.726	34.48
Hg^{2+}	2.531	2.580	2.615	2.650	7.403	4.007	38.28

Figure 2: The van't Hoff's plots of $\ln K_f$ vs. $1000/T$ for $M^{n+}-L$ complexes, (A) Cu^{+2} , (B) Pd^{+2} , (C) Co^{+2} , (D) Ni^{+2} , (E) Mn^{+2} , (F) Cr^{+2} , (G) Pb^{+2} , (H) Hg^{+2} in methanol.

Figure 3: Spectrophotometric absorption spectra of PMBP-TSC-metal ions in methanol (A) Cu^{+2} (B) Pd^{+2} (C) Co^{+2} (D) Ni^{+2} (E) Mn^{+2} (F) Cr^{+2} (G) Pb^{+2} (H) Hg^{+2} and (1) Metal, (2) ligand, (3) M-complexes.

The thermodynamic information in table 1 representation that, the negative values of free energy (ΔG°) specify that the complexation process is spontaneous. ΔH° for the formation of complexes with Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cr^{2+} , pb^{2+} and Hg^{2+} is positive. It means that the formation of these complexes is enthalpy desirable in all cases the complexes. The values for thermodynamic quantities ΔH° and ΔS° were computed from the slopes and intercepts of the corresponding $\ln K_f$ vs. $1000/T$ plots (fig. 2) by applying a linear least square analysis according to the van't Hoff equation (5).

$$2.303 \log K_f = -\left(\frac{\Delta H}{RT}\right) + \left(\frac{\Delta S}{R}\right) \quad (5)$$

Spectrophotometric study

The absorption spectra of PMBP-TSC, metal ions and its respective complexes in methanol in the wavelength range 200-400 nm are shown in (fig. 3). A wavelength shift of about 10 nm towards longer wavelength was observed for all the complexes from the ligand spectra in methanol.

The stoichiometry of the metal complexes was examined by the mole ratio method. Samples of the resulting plots for all eight M^{n+} -L complexes are shown in (fig.5), and it is clear that 1:1 (metallic ions to ligand) complexes are formed in solution. All the resulting absorbance -mole ratio data were best fitted to the equation (6), which extra support the formation of ML complexes in solution.

$$K_f [L]^2 + (1 + K_f (C_M - C_L)) [L] - C_L = 0 \quad (6)$$

The complexation formation constant from spectrometric titration was calculated using Benesi-Hidebrand plot (equation-7)

$$\frac{C_L \times C_M}{\frac{A}{\epsilon_{ML}} + (C_L + C_M)}$$

Fig-7 represented the spectrophotometry titration Plotting $C_M \times C_L / A$ versus $C_M + C_L$ for eight ML-complexes straight lines were produced and interpreting our result of the formation of 1:1 complexes [M: L] [21]. In this graph of being the formation constant in Table-2 which is equal to (slope/intercept) and ϵ_{ML} is the molar adsorption co-efficient of the complex which is equal to $(1/\text{slop})$. From the results it is clear that the stability of the M-L complexes vary in the order $\text{Pd}^{+2} > \text{Cr}^{+2} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{+2} > \text{Pb}^{+2} > \text{Hg}^{+2} > \text{Co}^{+2} > \text{Cu}^{+2}$ at 25°C temperature.

Synthesis of solid metal-complexes formation.

The following general method was used in the synthesis of metal complexes, metal salts ($\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{PdCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CrCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was added respectively to a 25 ml of methanolic solution of the legend (PMBP-TSC) in 1:1 mole ratio. The resulting mixture was heated at $60-70^\circ\text{C}$ on a water bath for 30-40 min. The obtained colored precipitate was filtered off, washed with diethyl ether and finally dried and purified by ethanol.

Table 2: Stoichiometry ratio of Mn^{+2} - L complexes in MeOH using from the conductometric titration and mole ratio methods at 25°C temp.

Complex	UV- vis. λ_{max} , nm	log K_f		Stoichiometry		Λ_m ($\text{S cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$)
		spectrophotometry	condctometry	M.R	Cond.	
Cu^{2+}	249	2.87	2.440	1:1	1:1	48.3
Pd^{2+}	235	3.27	3.020	1:1	1:1	17.2
Co^{2+}	250	3.029	2.515	1:1	1:1	72.3
Ni^{2+}	250	3.228	2.603	1:1	1:1	30.0
Mn^{2+}	246	3.249	2.619	1:1	1:1	79.7
Cr^{2+}	238	3.25	2.634	1:1	1:1	85.6
Pb^{2+}	245	3.20	2.549	1:1	1:1	14.3
Hg^{2+}	243	3.13	2.529	1:1	1:1	106.4

Table 3: IR data for ligand PMBP-TSC and their metal-complexes.

No.	(NH ₂)	N-H	phenyl	Pyr. ring	C=S	O-H	C=N	N-N	(M-S)
Ligand	3340	3153	1556,1496	1475	837,750	3440	1593	1093	-
C-1	3284	-	1560,1523	1477	858,746	3639	1598	1090	495
C-2	3367	-	1566,1521	1483	854,792	3608	1598	1072	497
C-3	3406	-	1562	1492	852,796	3527	1597	1074	505
C-4	3331	-	1523	1496	846,788	-	1560	1074	486
C-5	3344	-	1494	1475	835,748	3506	1570	1122	491
C-6	3334	-	1494	1475	835,748	3462	1590	1072	499
C-7	3294	-	1500	1419	835,758	-	1560	1068	493
C-8	3280	-	1544	1498	839,758	3460	1598	1058	491

Table 4: ¹H NMR data for data for ligand PMBP-TSC and their metal-complexes.

Ligand/complex	N(4)H	Methyl proton(ppm)	Aryl protone(ppm)	HC=N	N(5)H
Ligand	10.407	1.90	7.09-7.90	9.37	8.67
C-1	-	1.14	7.17-7.95	3.61	7.97
C-2	-	1.78	7.18-7.97	3.39	8.35
C-3	-	1.72	7.00-8.26	3.38	8.30
C-4	-	1.80	7.42-7.99	3.42	8.37
C-5	-	1.32	7.15-7.65	3.77	9.94
C-6	-	1.62	7.21-7.96	3.84	9.03
C-7	-	1.99	7.33-7.83	3.56	8.32
C-8	-	1.24	7.11-7.71	3.46	7.82

Table 5: Structural formula of the ligand and their M-complexes with respective mass spectral analysis.

No.	M-complex/ Ligand	structure	Molar mass
PMBP-TS C	(<i>Z</i>)-2-((3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1 <i>H</i> -pyrazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methylene)hydrazinecarbo thioamide.		C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ OS MS = <i>m/z</i> : 351.7(M ⁺) 41%. Formula weight = 351.43
PMBP-TS C-Cu	((<i>Z,Z</i>)- <i>N</i> '-((3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1 <i>H</i> -pyrazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methylene) carbamoyl thio) copper(II) chloride.		C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClCuN ₅ OS MS = <i>m/z</i> : 448[M-1] ⁺ 15%, 447[M-2] ⁺ 57%. Formula weight = 449.24
PMBP-TS C-Pd	((<i>Z,Z</i>)- <i>N</i> '-((3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1 <i>H</i> -pyrazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methylene) carbamoyl thio)Palladium(II) chloride.		C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₅ OPdS MS = <i>m/z</i> : 491.9(M ⁺) 30%, 493.9[M+1] ⁺ 20%, 490.9[M-1] ⁺ 24%, 489.9[M-2] ⁺ 36%. Formula weight =492.29
PMBP-TS C-Co	((<i>Z,Z</i>)- <i>N</i> '-((3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1 <i>H</i> -pyrazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methylene) carbamoyl thio) cobalt(II)chloride.		C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClCoN ₅ OS Mass = <i>m/z</i> : 444.01(M ⁺) 13%. Formula weight =444.80
PMBP-TS C-Ni	((<i>Z,Z</i>)- <i>N</i> '-((3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1 <i>H</i> -pyrazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methylene) carbamoyl thio) nickel(II)chloride.		C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₅ NiOS MS = <i>m/z</i> : 442.0[M-1] ⁺ 66%, 441[M-2] ⁺ 36%. Formula weight =443.5

PMBP-TS C-Mn	(((Z,Z)-N'-((3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methylene) carbamoyl)thio)manganese(II)chloride.		$C_{18}H_{16}ClMnN_5OS$ MS = m/z : 440(M^+)8%, 438.9[M-1] ⁺ 8%, 437.8[M-2] ⁺ 14%. Formula weight =440.81
PMBP-TS C-Cr	(((Z,Z)-N'-((3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methylene) carbamoyl)thio)chromium(II)chloride.		$C_{18}H_{16}ClCrN_5OS$ MS = m/z : 438[M+1] ⁺ 10%. Formula weight = 437.87
PMBP-TS C-Pb	(((Z,Z)-N'-((3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methylene) carbamoyl)thio)lead(II)nitrite.		$C_{18}H_{16}N_6O_3PbS$ MS = m/z : 558[M-46] ⁺ [23] Formula weight = 603.6
PMBP-TS C-Hg	(((Z,Z)-N'-((3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)(phenyl)methylene) carbamoyl)thio)mercury(II)chloride.		$C_{18}H_{16}ClHgN_5OS$ MS = m/z : 586.2(M^+) 22%, 588.2[M+1] ⁺ 26%. Formula weight =586.46

Table 6: Thermal data of the ligand and M-complexes (C-1 to C-8).

Complex	m.p (°C)	Color	Temp. Rang (°C)	% Mass loss		Expected nature of decomposition
				found	Calcd.	
[Cu(PMBP-TSC). H ₂ O]	235	Green	100 200 600	0.87 5.04 77.27	- 4.01 78.13	- Loss of One coordinated H ₂ O Loss of ligand part
[Pd(PMBP-TSC).H ₂ O] H ₂ O	>350	Orange	100 200 800	3.31 7.09 67.09	3.65 7.31 71.09	Loss of One hydrated H ₂ O Loss of one co-ordinated H ₂ O Loss of ligand part
[Co(PMBP-TSC).3H ₂ O]	281	Grey	100 200 800	0.62 11.38 66.34	- 12.14 62.72	- Loss of three coordinated H ₂ O Loss of Pyrazolone moiety
[Ni(PMBP-TSC).2H ₂ O]	348	Dirty green	100 200 850	2.04 9.21 80.43	- 8.1 78.72	- Loss of two coordinated H ₂ O Loss of ligand part
[Mn(PMBP-TSC).H ₂ O]	215	Brown	100 200 800	0.95 5.48 80.21	- 4.08 79.62	- Loss of one coordinated H ₂ O Loss of ligand part
[Cr(PMBP-TSC).3H ₂ O]. H ₂ O	220	Dark green	100 200 800	6.29 12.18 77.92	4.12 12.33 80.16	Loss of one H ₂ O Loss of three coordinated H ₂ O Loss of ligand part

[Pb(PMBP-TSC)]	185	Yellow	100 200 800	0.7 2.65 60	- - 62.65	- - Loss of ligand part
[Hg(PMBP-TSC) .H ₂ O]	206	Light yellow	100 200 400	1.17 3.52 60	- 3.14 59.47	- Loss of one coordinated H ₂ O Loss of ligand part

Table7: The antimicrobial activity of metal complexes in ($\mu\text{g/mL}$).

T	Antibacterial			Antifungal		Antimalarial
	<i>P.aeruginosa</i> MTCC 1688	<i>S.aureus</i> MTCC96	<i>S.pyogenus</i> MTCC 442	<i>C.albicans</i> MTCC227	<i>A.clavatus</i> MTCC282	<i>P.falciparum</i> Mean IC50
C-1	500	500	500	>1000	500	1.06
C-2	200	125	200	500	1000	1.44
C-3	200	100	100	1000	>1000	1.19
C-4	250	200	125	500	>1000	0.87
C-5	200	250	250	1000	500	1.53
C-6	100	250	125	500	500	0.87
C-7	200	500	550	1000	>1000	0.98
C-8	100	250	250	1000	>1000	1.47
Ampicilin	100	250	100	-	-	-
Greseofulvin	-	-	-	500	100	-
quinine	-	-	-	-	-	0.28

Figure 4: Mole ratio plots of absorbance vs. $[L]/[M]$ for (A) Cu^{+2} (B) Pd^{+2} (C) Co^{+2} (D) Ni^{+2} (E) Mn^{+2} (F) Cr^{+2} (G) Pb^{+2} (H) Hg^{+2} in methanol of respective complex wavelength at R.T.

Characterization of complexes

IR spectra

The IR spectra of ligand and their complexes are summarized in table 3. IR spectrum shows an important band at $\sim 3300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, ~ 1475 are assigned to $\nu(\text{NH}_2)$ and pyrazolone ring in ligand as well as complexes. The strong band $\nu(\text{N-H})$ at $\sim 3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. After complexation, these band missing in the complex, but new bands at $\sim 748\text{-}780 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\nu(\text{C-S})$ from these observations, it is concluded that the ligand react in thio-enol form of enolic protons

which are replaced by metal ion in the complexes. In the low frequency at $\sim 490\text{-}505 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region is $\nu(\text{M-S})$ bond. IR spectra of the ligand and complexes discovered band at $\sim 1560\text{-}1590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ observed to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$. The band for $\nu(\text{N-N})$ is observed at $\sim 1070\text{-}1090 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

¹H NMR spectra

¹H NMR data of the ligand and all complexes were recorded in DMSO- d_6 solution show in table 4 and fig 6. The ligand and their complexes appeared as a singlet in the range 3.30-3.85 ppm due to

methyl proton. In several cases, it is complicated to assign each signal to a particular methyl when the signals of CH₃ groups overlapped. The aromatic protons for the ligand observed as a multiplet at 7.09-7.90 ppm. During the complexation, these signals appeared at 7.10-8.00 ppm. The signal due to the -N(4)H

proton for the ligand at 10.40 ppm which disappears in the in all metal complexes. On complexation, -N(5)H signal shifted.

Mass spectra

The structure of ligand (PMBP-TSC) and metal complexes conformed from mass spectra, which shown in table 5 with their steady molecular ion peak (*m/z*) and the intensity (%) respectively.

Figure 5: Benesi -Hildebrand graph of M-L complexes.

Figure-6: ¹H NMR results for ligand (T-1) and metal complexes (C-1 to C-8).

Thermal studies

In the present study, heating rates were suitably controlled at 100 [mL min⁻¹] under nitrogen atmosphere the temperature range of R. T. -1000°C using an aluminum cell the thermogravimetric analysis results of all complexes described in table 6. The result showed the metal complexes C-1 to C-8 degradation essentially in three stages. The first stage appeared within the temperature range of R.T.-100°C, which may explain for the loss of hydrated water molecules and the second stage appeared within the temperature range 100-200°C was due to the removal of coordinated water molecules. In the third stage, metal complexes C-1 to C-7 at ~ 600-800°C and C-8 at the 400°C temperature range corresponds to the decomposition of a ligand part with theoretical and calculated mass loss value in %.

Biological

Here we have used previously reported methods for screening. Antibacterial [23], antifungal [23] and anti-malarial activities [24] of all metal complexes were shown in table 7. The results were compared with standard drug ampicillin for antibacterial activity, griseofulvin for antifungal activity and quinine for anti-malarial activity.

Compound C-2 exhibit moderate activity against *P. aeruginosa* (MTCC 1688). Compound C-2, C-3, C-4, C-6 shown good activity where compound C-5, C-8 exhibit moderate activity against *S. aureus* (MTCC 96). Compound C-3 exhibit moderate activity against *S. pyogenes* (MTCC 442). Compound C-2, C-4 and C-6 exhibit moderate activity against *C. albicans*. The anti-malarial activity of all compounds is good, but not higher than the standard.

CONCLUSIONS

The stability constants of the complex formation were investigated by applying the UV-vis spectrophotometry and conductometric method at different temperatures. Based on the results, the 1:1 (Metal: PMBP-TSC) complex stoichiometry and stability order of the metal complexes is Pd⁺² > Cr⁺² > Ni⁺² > Mn⁺² > Pb⁺² > Hg⁺ > Co⁺² > Cu⁺² at 25°C temperature as evaluated by these techniques.

In this thermodynamic study, the negative value of the ΔG suggested that the ligand is capable of forming stable complexes and that the process will proceed spontaneously, while the positive sign of the entropy shows that ΔS is the driving force of the complexation reaction in this complex formation. These facts mean that ΔG is always negative and ΔS are always positive.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Department of Chemistry, Gujarat University Ahmadabad, for providing the necessary facilities and also thankful to UGC-Info net & INFLIBNET Gujarat University for providing e-source facilities. One of us (Rashmi B. Patel) is thankful to RGNF- F1-17.1-GUJ-19894 for financial support.

REFERENCES

1. N. A. Khalil, E. M. Ahmed, K. O. Mohamed, Y. M. Nissan, S. A. Zaitone, Synthesis and biological evaluation of new pyrazolone-pyridazine conjugates as anti-inflammatory and analgesic agents. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chem.*, 22 (2014) 2080-2089.
2. G. Saidachary, K. Veera Prasad, D. Divya, A. Singh, U. Ramesh, B. Sridhar, B. China Raju, convenient one pot

synthesis, anti-mycobacterial and anticancer activities of novel benzoxazolones and pyrazolone, *European Journal of Medicinal Chem.*, 764 (2014) 60-69.

3. M. Guo, J. Guo, D. Jia, H. Liu, L. Liu, A. Liu, F. Li, Synthesis, properties, and Mechanism of two novel photoisomerization pyrazolones in the solid state *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 271 (2013) 1035.
4. V. M. Leovac, G. A. Bogdanovic, L. S. Jovanovic, L. Jokovic, V. Markovic, M. D. Jokovic, S. M. Dencic, A. Isakovic, I. Markovic, F. W. Heinemann, S. Trifunovic, I. Dalovic, Synthesis, characterization and anti tumor activity of polymeric Copper (II) complexes with thiosemicarbazones of 3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl-3-pyrazoline-4-carboxaldehyde and 5-oxo-3-phenyl-3-pyrazoline-4-carboxaldehyde. *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, 105 (2011) 1413-1421.
5. A. K. El-Sawaf, A. A. Fatah Nassar, El-S. El-Samanody, Spectral and biological studies of copper (II) complexes of 4-benzoyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazoline-5-one N(4)-substituted thiosemicarbazones. *Science Journal of chem.*, 2 (2014) 17-26.
6. N. Raman, A. Selvan, P. Manisankar, Spectral, magnetic, biocidal screening, DNA binding and photocleavage studies of mononuclear Cu(II) and Zn(II) metal complexes of tricoordinate heterocyclic Schiff base ligands of pyrazolone and semicarbazide/thiosemicarbazide based derivatives. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A*, 76 (2010) 161-173.
7. S. Sathiyaraj, K. Sampath, C. Jayabalakrishnan, Synthesis, Spectral Characterization, DNA Binding, DNA Cleavage, and Antioxidant Studies of Ruthenium (III) Heterocyclic Thiosemicarbazone Complexes Synthesis and Reactivity in *Inorganic, Metal-Organic, and Nano-Metal Chem.*, 44 (2014) 161-212.
8. K. M. Vyas, R. N. Jadeja, D. Patel, R. V. Devkar, V. K. Gupta, Effect of ligand Substitution in pyrazolone based binary ternary Cu(II) complexes on DNA binding, Protein binding and anti cancer activity on A549 lung carcinoma cell line, *Polyhedron*, 80 (2014) 20-23.
9. J. Hu, L. Liu, D. Jia, J. Guo, X. Xie, D. Wu, R. Sheng, Crystal structure and photoisomerization behaviors of five novel pyrazolones derivatives containing furoyl Group, *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chem.*, 217(2011)117-124.
10. B. Pang, G. Liu, L. Liu and D. Jia, Studies on solid-state proton transfer along hydrogen bond of pyrazolone-ring, *Tetrahedron*, 61 (2005) 5926-5932.
11. O. H. Shehab, The effect of some Thiosemicarbazide derivatives and their complexes on Human Serum Cholinesterase Activity, *J. of university of Anbar for pure science*, 3 (2009) 2.
12. S. Pal, J. Marsddy, N. Suneetha, S. Nalla, High Speed Synthesis of Pyrazolones using Microwave-Assisted Neat

- Reaction Technology. *J. Braz Chem. Soc*, 19 (2008) 207-1214.
13. B. S. Jensen, The Synthesis of 1-phenyl -3- methyl-4-acyl pyrazolones-5. *Acta Chemica Scandinavica, Acta Chemica Scandinavica*, 13 (1959) 1668-1670.
 14. X.-c. Tang, D.-z. Jia, K. Liang, X.-g. Zhang, X. Xia, Z.-y. Zhou, Synthesis of Metal Complexes of 1-phenyl -3-methyl-4-benzoyl Pyrazolone-5-one Semicarbazone by Solide-State and Solution Reactions. *Synthesis and Reactivity in Inorganic, Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chem.*, 134 (2000) 23-29.
 15. S. A. Zaidi, N. Fatima, A COMPARATIVE STUDY FOR CHELATION OF IRON (II) AND IRON (II) WITH LEVODOPA-AN ANTIPARKINSONIANDRUG MOLECULE, *Eur. Chem. Bull.*, 3 (2014) 648-653.
 16. H. A. Benesi, J. H. Hildebrand, The Benesi-Hildebrand Methode for Determination of Kf for DA association and Values for DA CT absorption, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 71 (1949) 2703.
 17. G. Rounaghi, Z. Eshaghi, E. Ghiamati, Thermodynamic study of complex formation between 18-crown -6 and potassium ion in some binary non-aqueous solvents using a conductometric method, *Talanta*, 44 (1997) 275-282.
 18. E. A. Gomaa, Conductance Studies on Complex Formation between CaCl₂ and Ampicillin as Ligand in Water and In Methanol Solvent at Different Temperatures. *Reserch and Reviews*, E. M. Elleef, E. Helmy, *Reserch and Reviews: Journal of Pharmacy and harmaceutical Sciences*, 3 (2014) 3.
 19. H. Temel, U. Cakir, H.I. Ugras, Synthesis and Characterization of a Novel Oxovanadium (IV) Complex and Conductometric Studies with N,N0-bis(Salicylidene)-1,2-bis(p-amino phenoxy)ethane, *Synthesis and Reactivity in Inorganic and Metal-Organic Chem.*, 34 (2004) 819-831.
 20. M. R. Nasrabadi, F. Ahmadi, S. M. Pourmortazavi, M. R. Ganjali, K. Alizadeh, Conductometry study of complex formations between some substituted pyrimidies and some metal ions in acetonitrile and t *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 144 (2009) 97-101.
 21. A.S. Al-Attas, M. M. Habeeb, D. S. Al-Raimi, Sptrophotometric determination of some amino hetrocyclic donors through charge transfer complex formation with chloranilic acid in acetonitrile. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 148 (2009) 58-66.
 22. R. M. Silverstein, F. X. Webster, *Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds*, 6th Edn, p. 31, John Wiley & Sons, new york (1996).
 23. S. M. Prajapati, R. H. Vekariya, K. D. Patel, S. N. Panchal, H. D. Patel, D. P. Rajani, S. D. Rajani, Snthesis and in vitro antibacterial and antifungal evaluation of quinoline analogue azetidin and thiazolidin derivatives, *International Letters of Chemistry, Physics and Astronomy*, 20 (2014)195-210.
 24. S. M. Divatia, D. P. Rajani, S. D. Rajani, H. D. Patel, Novel thiosemicarbazone derivatives containig benzimidazole moiety ,*Arabian journal of chemistry*,10 (2014) 1016..

Citation: Hitesh D. Patel et al.. (2015) Pyrazolone Thiosemicarbazone Based Metal Complexes: Physico-Chemical Study, Synthesis and Biological Activity *j. of Physical and Chemical Sciences*.V3I2. DOI: 10.15297/JPCS.V3I2.03

Copyright: © 2015 Hitesh D. Patel. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.